

XOKKEYCHILAR FAOLIYATINING FIZIOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Xokkeychilar faoliyatining fiziologik xususiyatlari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: o‘yin qoidalari, burchak jarimalari, texnik-taktik harakatlar, tayyorgarlik davri, o‘rtacha harakat masofa, yurak urish tezligi.

PHYSIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF HOCKEY PLAYERS.

Abstract. This article discusses the physiological characteristics of hockey players.

Key words: rules of the game, corner penalties, technical-tactical actions, preparation period, average movement distance, heart rate.

ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ХОККЕИСТОВ.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются физиологические особенности хоккеистов.

Ключевые слова: правила игры, угловые штрафы, технико-тактические действия, период подготовки, средняя дистанция перемещения, частота пульса.

Kirish - chim ustidagi xokkey – futbol bilan juda ko‘p taktik va tuzilmaviy - o‘xshashliklarga ega bo‘lgan sport turi bo‘lib, u dunyoning eng mashhur o‘yini bilan ba‘zi bir taqqoslashlarni amalga oshirish imkonini beradi. Biroq, futbol bilan solishtirganda, xokkey o‘yining turli jihatlarini o‘rganishga bag‘ishlangan tadqiqotlar hajmi va sifati ancha past. O‘yin qoidalariga kiritilgan o‘zgartirishlar, masalan, cheksiz miqdordagi almashtirishlar (2014) va “o‘yindan tashqari holat” qoidasining bekor qilinishi (1998) xokkeychilarning o‘yin faoliyati xususiyatlariga ta‘sir ko‘rsatdi. Butun o‘yin davomida bir jamoadan o‘n sakkizta o‘yinchi o‘yinga jalb qilinishi mumkin. Murabbiy o‘yin tempini oshirish uchun zarur deb hisoblasa, istalgan vaqtda almashtirishni amalga oshirishi mumkin. O‘yinni har biri 15 daqiqadan 4 taymda, "burchak jarimalari"ga tayyorgarlik ko‘rish uchun to‘xtash vaqti bilan o‘tkazish murabbiylarga o‘yinga tez-tez jamoaviy tuzatishlar kiritish imkonini beradi.

Chim ustida xokkey bo‘yicha asosiy tadqiqotlar mahalliy (V.N. Seluyanov, S.K. Sarsaniya 1991, V.M. Kostyukevich, 2011, E.V. Fedotova, 2007, I.Yu. Shishkov, 2011) va chet ellik mutaxassislar (Bole Mahoney, & Wallace, 1994; Gosh, Gosvamy, Mazmudare va Mature, 1991; Johnston, Sproule, McMorris & Maile, 2004; Paun, van der Ploeg & Stern, 2008; Spencer., 2004, Jon Lythe, 2008) tomonidan olib borilgan. Asosiy e‘tibor o‘yinchilarning maydondagi harakatini tahlil qilishga, ularni portativ GPS qurilmalari yordamida o‘lchash (yurak urish tezligini kuzatish “Polar” tizimi yordamida amalga oshirilgan), shuningdek, erkak va ayol xokkeychilarning shaxsiy va jamoaviy texnik-taktik harakatlarni qayd etishga qaratilgan.

Chim ustidagi xokkey musobaqasi o‘yin davomida o‘yinchilar tomonidan bajariladigan texnik-taktik harakatlarning turli ketma-ketligi va xarakterini ifodalaydi. Bu raqib jamoalarning texnik mahoratiga va raqibning o‘yin davomida amal qiladigan taktik rejasiga bog‘liq.

O'rtacha bir o'yin uchun jamoaning texnik-taktik harakatlarining umumiy hajmi (TTH) 835 ta harakatni tashkil etadi, ulardan 34% to'p uzatish, 24% to'pni qabul qilish, 7% dribling, 12% to'pni raqibdan olib qo'yish, 12% (uzatmada) to'pni olib qo'yish, 9% aldab o'tishlar, 2% darvoza tomon zarbalar (uloqtirishlar)ga to'g'ri keladi (E.V. Fedotova, 2007). O'yin davomida maydon o'yinchisi tomonidan bajariladigan TTH hajmi va samaradorligi sezilarli darajada uning malakasi va maydonda bajaradigan funktsiyalariga bog'liq. 2.1-jadvalda turli roldagi xokkeychilarning TTH ko'rsatkichlari ko'rsatilgan (A.M. Nevmyanov bo'yicha, 1990).

Xokkeychilarning texnik va taktik mahorat darajasini aks ettiruvchi musobaqa faoliyatining muhim xususiyati bu TTH-ning ko'p qirraliligi, qo'llaniladigan texnik va taktika usullar ko'lamini, ularning turlari va amalga oshirish usullaridir. Xokkeychilarning mahoratini o'sishi bilan birga TTH hajmi, ayniqsa to'pni harakatda to'xtatishlar, va ularning samaradorligi 25 dan 80,6% gacha oshadi (V.M. Kostyukevich, 1991).

Chim ustida xokkeyda jarima burchagi alohida o'rin tutadi. Uzatma yoki to'g'ridan-to'g'ri zarba amalga oshirilganidan so'ng, statistika ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, to'plar umumiy holatlarning 40% hollarda raqiblar darvozasiga kiritiladi. Eng kuchli erkaklar jamoalari uchun jarima zarbasining samaradorligi 30-40% gacha, ayollar jamoalarida bu ko'rsatkich biroz pastroq - 25-30%ni tashkil etadi (E.V. Fedotova, 2007).

Zamonaviy xokkey o'zining jismoniy faolligida 1990 yildagi xokkeydan sezilarli farqlarga ega. Bu o'yin qoidalarini o'zgarishi bilan bog'liq. Oldingi tadqiqotlarda, o'yin roliga qarab, xokkeychilar turli xil jismoniy faollik ko'rsatishar edi.

1-jadval - Bir o'yinda har xil ampuladagi xokkeychilarning TTHning o'rtacha miqdoriy va sifat ko'rsatkichlari.

TTH	Hujumchi		Yarim himoyachi		Himoyachi	
	miqdor	sam-lik %	miqdor	sam-lik %	miqdor	sam-lik %
(Uzatmada) to'pni olib qo'yish	5,3	50,0	1,7	66,0	13,0	55,8
To'pni raqibdan olib qo'yish	5,3	18,8	11,7	22,6	13,5	29,6
Darvozaga hujum	2,7	12,5	8,6	20,0	-	-
Aldab o'tish	10,0	70,0	7,3	76,9	5,0	75,0
Dribling	6,0	88,9	10,3	100	3,8	93,3
Uzatma	16,0	64,6	26,0	78,2	28,5	71,0
To'pni to'xtatish	21,3	76,6	41,3	88,5	14,8	94,9
Jami TTH:	66,7	65,0	107,0	71,0	78,5	70,4

Maksimal va maksimalga yaqin tezlikka ega bo'lgan eng uzoq vaqt hujumchilar uchun qayd etilgan (tayyorgarlik davri va o'yin darajasiga qarab 13 dan 83 sekundgacha, 5,24–12,10%). Himoyachilar ulardan biroz orqada qolishmoqda (11 dan 69 soniyagacha, bu 3,64–9,96%). Yanada ko'proq ortda qolish yarim himoyachilarda kuzatilgan (6 dan 58 soniyagacha, mos ravishda 1,46–6,64%) (E.V. Fedotova, 2007, Исследования женских команд высокого уровня). Sportchilarning harakatlarini kuzatishning zamonaviy tizimi (GPS-navigatsiya) yordamida yanada aniqroq ma'lumotlar olindi.

GPS monitoringi natijalariga ko'ra, xokkeychining (hujumchi, erkaklar jamoasi) 60 daqiqalik o'yin vaqti ichida o'rtacha harakat masofasi (eski o'yin qoidalariga muvofiq) 8160 ± 428 m, shundan 19 km/soatdan yuqori tezlikda 479 ± 108 m ni tashkil etdi (6,1%). Yuqori intensivlik bilan har bir o'yinda o'rtacha 3,3 soniya davomiylik bilan 34 ± 12 marotaba tezlanish bajarilar edi.

O'yinning 1 va 2-bo'limlarida bosib o'tilgan masofalar o'rtasidagi farq o'rtacha 6,2% ga kamayar edi.

Xokkeychilarning holatini tavsiflovchi eng ko'p tadqiqotlar shotlandiyalik mutaxassis Jonston va boshqalar tomonidan amalga oshirilgan (2004). $19,5 \pm 2,5$ yoshli milliy chempionat darajasidagi 15 nafar shotlandiyalik xokkeychi nazorat guruhi sifatida jalb qilindi. Xokkeychining o'yindagi harakat faolligi % da aniqlandi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni ta'kidlash lozimki, harakatlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki: tik turish (4%), yurish (50,9%), yengil yugurish (29,6%), tez yugurish (10,1%), sprint (4,7%). Shu bilan birga, har bir o'yinda o'rtacha yurak urish tezligi $143 \pm 15,3$, maksimal 183 ± 11 zarba/daq ni tashkil etgan. Ma'lum bir yurak urish tezligida sarflangan o'yin vaqtining maksimal yurak urish tezligining $<75\%$ - o'yinning $37 \pm 18,8\%$ ni; maksimal yurak urish tezligining 75-85%, mos ravishda o'yinning $26,1 \pm 11,8\%$ ni; maksimal yurak urish tezligining 85-95% - o'yinning $34 \pm 17,4\%$ ni; maksimal yurak urish tezligining $>95\%$ - $4 \pm 3,0\%$ ni tashkil etdi. Jismoniy faollik va tinch turgan holatining nisbati 1:5,7 ($\pm 0,6$) nisbatida olingan. Har bir o'yinchi uchun o'rtacha sprintlar soni o'rtacha 5,7 s. davomiylik bilan 30 ± 6 marotaba tezlik bilan qo'zg'alishni (tezlanish) tashkil qildi.

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